

Estimation of the best time of year for maintenance of an onshore wind farm using time series*

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Abstract. This article reports on the best time of the year to carry out maintenance in a wind farm, considering as an indicator the lowest values of the average hourly output power of a 2 MW wind turbine. To achieve this, a mathematical model has been developed to characterize the wind resource in the study area, which has been fed with environmental data: wind speed, temperature and local pressure. The results indicate that the best time is from the beginning of February to the first fifteen days of March of each year. At a technical level, this study has the potential to search for and estimate the best weeks of the year to carry out maintenance in wind farms, leading to a trend of minimal impact on the production of electric energy in the wind farm.

Keywords: Wind farms · Maintenance · Smart Cities · Time series.